

Chemical examination of juice of *Citrus sinensis* variety Jaffa

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Abstract : Phytochemical examination of *Citrus sinensis* juice var. Jaffa resulted in the isolation of 5,7-dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavanone 7-O-rhamnosyl(1→2)glucoside which is a hitherto unreported compound.

Keywords : *Citrus sinensis*, Rutaceae, 5,7-Dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavanone 7-O-rhamnosyl(1→2)glucoside.

Introduction

Citrus sinensis (L) Osbeck var. Jaffa (syn. *C. aurantium* L. var. *sinensis*) belongs¹ to Rutaceae family, and it is commonly known as sweet orange or mosambi. It is known to cure² skin, dental and oral diseases. It possesses³ anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. A survey of literature shows that the variety Jaffa has not been subjected to chemical analysis so far and the present investigation has therefore been undertaken.

Melting points were determined on Ganson Electric Melting Point Apparatus. IR spectra were recorded on Hitachi 570 Infrared Spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were obtained on Bruker AC 300 F MHz NMR Spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on VG 70 S 11-250J GCMS-DS Mass spectrometer.

Fruits (2 kg) of Jaffa were collected from Horticulture Department, Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar. Fruits were squeezed to get juice which was washed with ethyl acetate four times. Extractives were concentrated over water bath under reduced pressure to obtain a viscous mass which was mixed with silica gel (60-120 mesh), dried over water bath, subjected to silica gel column chromatography, and one compound was isolated which was marked as A.

Results and discussion

Compound A (5-Hydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavanone 7-O-rhamnosyl(1→2)glucoside, 1) :

It was obtained on elution with ethyl acetate, and it crystallized from methanol, 50 mg, m.p. 240 °C. It res-

ponded to Mg/HCl test. Alcoholic FeCl₃ test : brown colour. Found : C, 55.76; H, 5.76. C₂₉H₃₆O₁₅ requires : C, 55.70; H, 5.71%. UV λ_{max} (nm) 286, 346 (MeOH); 282, 338 (MeOH + NaOAc); 312, 377 (MeOH + AlCl₃). IR ν_{max} (nujol, cm⁻¹) : 722, 815, 972, 1069, 1096, 1133, 1204, 1277, 1377, 1462, 1606, 1648, 2854, 2924, 3421. MS (m/z) : 624 (M⁺, not observed), 596 (M - 28), 476 (100%), 436, 422, 377, 333, 319, 275. Molisch Test : positive. Kiliani Hydrolysis : glucose and rhamnose confirmed by direct comparison using paper chromatography; and aglycone : 5,7-dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavanone (m.p. 205-206 °C, lit.⁴ m.p. 207 °C). Kiliani hydrolysis of permethylated naringin and that of compound A afforded 3,4,6-tri-O-methylglucose and 2,3,4-tri-O-methylrhamnose in each case. Acetate of the glycoside : Ac₂O/Py, m.p. 110 °C. ¹H NMR of glycoside acetate (δ, CDCl₃) : 1.14 (3H, d, J 7.5 Hz, Me), 1.956, 1.962, 1.968, 1.974, 2.036, 2.039 (3H each, 6s, 6 × OAc),

Fig. 1. Compound isolated from *Citrus sinensis*. 5,7-Dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavanone 7-O-rhamnosyl(1→2)glucoside

2.379 (3H, s, OAc), 3.83 (3H, s, OMe), 3.85 (3H, s, OMe), 2.80–5.50 (15H, m, 12 sugar protons, H-2, 2 × H-3), 6.28 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 6.38 (1H, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 7.1 (3H, m, H-2', H-5' and H-6').

The brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride indicated it to be a phenolic compound. It responded to Mg/HCl colour reaction suggesting it to be a flavonoid. IR depicted the presence of CO (1648 cm^{-1}) and OH (3421 cm^{-1}) groups. Elemental analysis indicated its molecular formula $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_{15}$ and molecular mass 624. A bathochromic shift of compound A with AlCl_3 indicated a free OH at C-5. No shift with NaOAc suggested OH-7 to be blocked. ^1H NMR of the acetate (δ , CDCl_3) showed a doublet at 6.28 (J 2.5 Hz) for one proton which could be H-6. Another doublet for one proton at 6.38 (J 2.5 Hz) was assignable to H-8. A multiplet for three protons at 7.1 could be three protons of B-ring. In the aliphatic section, a doublet for three protons at 1.14 (J 7.5 Hz) could be a methyl present on a carbon bearing one proton. Six singlets at 1.956, 1.962, 1.968, 1.974, 2.036 and 2.039, each for three protons, could be six aliphatic acetoxy groups, hinting two sugar units joined together in the molecule of compound A. Another singlet for three protons at 2.379 could be a phenolic acetoxy group. Two singlets at 3.83 and 3.85, each for three protons, could be two methoxy groups. A multiplet in the range 2.80–5.50, for fifteen protons, could be twelve sugar protons and three protons of C-ring of a flavanone. This data suggested compound A to be flavanone glycoside. Kiliani hydroly-

sis and paper chromatography confirmed the sugars to be glucose and rhamnose; and aglycone to be 5,7-dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavanone (2). Kiliani hydrolysis of permethylated naringin and that of compound A afforded 3,4,6-tri-*O*-methylglucose and 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methylrhamnose in each case confirming thereunder that sugar linkages are similar in the two flavanones. This data suggested compound A to be 5,7-dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavanone 7-*O*-rhamnosyl(1→2)glucoside (1) which is a hitherto unreported compound. *Citrus* plants are known to contain naringin⁵, and the present compound is 4'-*O*-methyl-3'-methoxynaringin (1).

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